

The background of the slide is a collage of various fruits and vegetables. The word 'NUTRITION' is formed by these items, with each letter being a different shape and color, representing different food groups. The letters are arranged in a slightly curved path across the top and middle of the slide. A white rectangular box with a thin orange border is centered over the middle of the word, containing the main title text.

NUTRITION AND HEALTH EATING HABITS

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EAT *well*
MOVE *daily*
HYDRATE *often*
SLEEP *lots*
LOVE *your body*

repeat for **LIFE**

WHAT IS NUTRITION?

Nutrition is defined as the science of foods, nutrients and other substances they contain; and of their actions within the body including ingestion, digestion, absorption, metabolism and excretion. While this summarizes the physiological dimensions, nutrition has social, psychological and economic dimensions too.

WHAT ARE NUTRIENTS?

- Nutrients are the constituents in food that must be supplied to the body in suitable amounts.
- These include **carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals, vitamins, water** and **fiber**. We need a wide range of nutrients to keep ourselves healthy. Most foods contain more than one nutrient such as milk has proteins, fats, etc.
- Nutrients can be classified as macronutrients and micronutrients on the basis of the required quantity to be consumed by us everyday.

Proteins are large, complex molecules that play many critical roles in the body. They do most of the work in cells and are required for the structure, function, and regulation of the body's tissues and organs.

PROTEINS

Protein-Rich Foods with no meat or nuts!

Hummus
2 Tbsp. = 2g

Broccoli
3/4 cup = 2g

Popcorn
2 cups = 2g

Avocado
1/2 = 2g

Whole Grain Crackers
15 = 3g

Tortilla
8-inch = 3g

Yogurt
1/2 cup = 5g

Roasted Chickpeas
1/4 cup = 5g

String Cheese
1 = 6g

Cheddar Cheese
1 oz. = 6g

Whole Grain Bread
1 slice = 6g

Hard-Boiled Egg
1 large = 6g

California Roll
5 pieces = 6g

Sunflower Seed Butter
2 Tbsp = 7g

Milk, dairy or soy
1 cup = 8g

Edamame, in pods
1 cup = 9g

Vegetarian Burger
or "Chicken" Patty
9 g

Tofu
3 oz. = 9g

Cheese Tortellini
3/4 cup = 10g

Slice of cheese pizza,
from 14" pizza
12g

FATS

Fats are a type of nutrient that you get from your diet. It is essential to eat some fats, though it is also harmful to eat too much. The fats you eat give your body energy that it needs to work properly. During exercise, your body uses calories from carbohydrates you have eaten.

VITAMINS

- A **vitamin** is an organic molecule (or a set of closely related molecules called vitamers) that are essential to an organism in small quantities for proper metabolic function.
- Essential nutrients cannot be synthesized in the organism in sufficient quantities for survival, and therefore must be obtained through the diet.
- There are two types of vitamins:
 - Water-Soluble
 - Fat-Soluble

HEALTHY FOOD

VITAMIN CHART

VITAMIN A (FAT SOLUBLE) FOR Normal Growth and Development, Normal Night Vision & Healthy Epithelium, Antioxidant. Deficiency leads to : Retarded Growth, Night Blindness, Glossed Eyeballs, Dry Scaly Skin, Cornea, Keratomata, Conjunctiva, Xerophthalmia.	
VITAMIN B1 (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Growth, Appetite, Normal Metabolism, Memory and Muscular Function. Deficiency leads to : Beriberi, Loss in Weight, Loss of Appetite, Emaciation, Unchecked Carbohydrate Metabolism.	
VITAMIN B2 (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Growth, Healthy Skin, Mouth & Eyes. Deficiency leads to : Retarded Growth, Dark Vision, Photophobia, Keratitis, Blepharitis, Tongue, Perosis, Dermatitis.	
VITAMIN B (P.P. FACTOR) (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Proper Carbohydrate Metabolism, Nervous System. Deficiency leads to : Pellagra, Dermatitis, Dementia, Psychosis, Diarrhoea.	
VITAMIN B6 (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Proper Metabolism of Amino Acids, Glucose-Fermentation, Anti-Emetic. Deficiency leads to : Anemia, Atrophic Lymph, Tissues, Poor Response against Diseases.	
VITAMIN B12 (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Red Blood Cells, Nerve Metabolism, Healthy Nervous Tissues. Deficiency leads to : Pernicious Anemia.	
VITAMIN C (WATER SOLUBLE) FOR Healthy Growth, Good Skin & Teeth, Rapid Blood Vessels, Rapid Healing, Resistance against Flu & Colds. Deficiency leads to : Scurvy, Swollen Gums, Bleeding of Blood Capillaries.	
VITAMIN D (FAT SOLUBLE) FOR Proper Utilization of Calcium & Phosphorus, Formation of Bones and Teeth. Deficiency leads to : Rickets, Poor Growth, Weak Teeth & Bones, Bone Pain.	
VITAMIN E (FAT SOLUBLE) FOR Normal Metabolism. Deficiency leads to : Starchy, Muscular Paralysis.	
VITAMIN K (FAT SOLUBLE) FOR Normal Blood Coagulation, and Liver Functioning. Deficiency Leads to : Hemorrhage.	

SOURCE: DELHI UNIVERSITY

MINERALS

- Minerals in food are the elements present in food that are required by our body to develop and function properly.
- We can deduce that minerals are inorganic substances required by the human body to function correctly. The human body requires varying amounts of minerals daily in order to build strong bones and muscles. It also helps to maintain various bodily functions.
- For example, we need more calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, potassium and chloride than we do iron, zinc, iodine, selenium and copper.

ROUGHAGE/FIBRE

- Fiber, also known as roughage, is the part of plant-based foods (grains, fruits, vegetables, nuts, and beans) that the body can't break down.
- It passes through the body undigested, keeping your digestive system clean and healthy, easing bowel movements, and flushing cholesterol and harmful carcinogens out of the body.

WATER

- Water is an inorganic compound with the chemical formula H_2O .
- It is a transparent, tasteless, odorless, and nearly colorless chemical substance, and it is the main constituent of Earth's hydrosphere and the fluids of all known living organisms.
- Everyone should drink at least 2.5 to 3 litres of water each day.

Daily calorie needs based on age, gender, and activity level

Age (Years)	Gender	Sedentary (Not Active)	Moderately Active	Active
2-3	Male or female	1,000	1,000	1,000
4-8	Male	1,200 – 1,400	1,400 – 1,600	1,600 – 2,000
	Female	1,200 – 1,400	1,400 – 1,600	1,400 – 1,800
9-13	Male	1,600 – 2,000	1,800 – 2,200	2,000 – 2,600
	Female	1,400 – 1,600	1,600 – 2,000	1,800 – 2,200
14-18	Male	2,000 – 2,400	2,400 – 2,800	2,800 – 3,200
	Female	1,800	2,000	2,400
19-30	Male	2,400 – 2,600	2,600 – 2,800	3,000
	Female	1,800 – 2,000	2,000 – 2,200	2,400
31-50	Male	2,200 – 2,400	2,400 – 2,600	2,800 – 3,000
	Female	1,800	2,000	2,200
51 and older	Male	2,000 – 2,200	2,200 – 2,400	2,400 – 2,800
	Female	1,600	1,800	2,000 – 2,200

Adapted from US Department of Agriculture and US Department of Health and Human Services. *Dietary Guidelines for Americans, 2010*. 7th ed. Washington, DC US Government Printing Office 2010.
<http://www.health.gov/dietaryguidelines/2010.asp>. Accessed March 18, 2014

	0-6 mo	1-3 years	4-8 years	Males 9-13	Females 9-13
Protein (g/day)	9.1	13	19	34	34
Carbohydrates (g/day)	60*	130	130	130	130
Fat (g/d--AI)	31*	ND	ND	ND	ND
Fiber g/d	ND	19*	25	31	26
Vitamin D (µg/d)	5*	5*	5*	5*	5*
Vitamin B12 (mg/d)	0.4*	0.9	1.2	1.8	1.8
Folate (µg/d)	65*	150	200	300	300
Calcium (mg/d)	210*	500*	800*	1300*	1300*
Iron (mg/d)	0.27*	7	10	8	8

From [Food and Nutrition Board](#), The Institute of Medicine, National Academies of Sciences ND: Not determined

* : AI - Adequate Intake

Bold: RDA - Recommended Daily Allowance

- A balanced diet is one which includes a variety of foods in adequate amounts and correct proportions to meet the day's requirements of all essential nutrients such as proteins, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, minerals, water, and fibre.
- Such a diet helps to promote and preserve good health and also provides a safety margin or reserve of nutrients to withstand short durations of deprivation when they are not supplied by the diet.

BALANCED DIET

FOOD PYRAMID

HEALTHY EATING PYRAMID

HEALTHY EATING

- Healthy eating means eating a variety of foods that give you the nutrients you need to maintain your health, feel good, and have energy. These nutrients include protein, carbohydrates, fat, water, vitamins, and minerals.
- Eating healthy means following a healthy eating pattern that includes a variety of nutritious foods and drinks. It also means getting the number of calories that's right for you (not eating too much or too little).

Kid's Healthy Eating Plate

A central white sign with black text is surrounded by a variety of fresh fruits. On the left, there are several bright orange oranges and a few red apples. On the right, there are clusters of purple and green grapes. At the top, there are two brown kiwis and a green apple. At the bottom, there are several ripe red strawberries. The entire scene is set against a background that transitions from yellow at the top to light green at the bottom.

HEALTHY

EATING

HABITS

Healthy eating habits for children

#Superheroes #SafeFoodtokids

Eat healthy food

Avoid junk food

Drink milk every day

Avoid fizzy drinks

Eat in small portions

Don't overeat

Eat with clean hands

Dirty hands carry germs

Every Child should have 6 meals in a day.

Small portion meals should be taken at an interval of 2 to 3 hours.

Eat Breakfast every single day of the week.

Breakfast is the most important meal of the day.

Eat a light, i.e., low in fat contents, dinner.

Prefer having soups, salads, etc.. as dinner

Drink at least 8 glasses of water in a day, approx. about 3 litres each day.

Eat green leafy vegetables at least 2 bowls each day.

Eat at least 7 eggs per week.

Eat non vegetarian items like chicken, etc.. Once or twice per week.

Eat at least 2 servings of fruit each day for whole 7 days.

Eat at least Two to Three bowls of salad each day.

Drink Two glasses of milk each day for complete week.

Say a big NO to junk food.

Avoid eating sweets frequently in a week.

Have 1 serving of sweets once in 2 – 3 weeks.

Wash your Hands before every meal.

IMPORTANCE OF HEALTHY EATING

- Keeps skin, teeth, and eyes healthy;
- Supports muscles;
- Helps achieve and maintain a healthy weight;
- Strengthens bones;
- Supports brain development;
- Supports healthy growth;
- Boosts immunity; and
- Helps the digestive system function.

CONCLUSION

- Nutrition is the science that deals with the complete metabolic process of eating and digesting of food and its conversion to energy, so that our body can function properly.
- Nutrients are the various chemical and biological constituents that are present in our food which are the main source which helps in body functions.
- Carbohydrates, fats and proteins constitute **MACRONUTRIENTS**, whereas, Vitamins, minerals and fiber constitute **MICRONUTRIENTS**.
- Our body is made up of 70% of water.
- Healthy eating habits are one of the most useful ways, in today's time, to achieve the best achievable health for today's generation.

THANK YOU

EAT HEALTHY